

Heckscher-Ohlin's Theory of International Trade and its Evaluation

Dr. S. Jeyarajah

Department of Economics
Faculty of Commerce and Management
Eastern University, Sri Lanka
jeyarajahs@esn.ac.lk

Introduction

Many theories in literature illuminate the international trade patterns of nations. Over time, economists have developed theories to explain the mechanisms of international trade. They are categorised into classical and modern theories of international trade. The classical theory of trade is based on the labour cost theory of value. These theories are from the perspective of a country. The classical theory of comparative advantage explains that trade can occur because of differences in the productivity of labour between countries (Salvatore, 2004). However, this theory does not explain the causes of the difference in productivity. The Ricardian model of comparative advantage explains much of world trade from Roman times to World War II. During the World War, the nations were agricultural economies with a small manufacturing sector. Grains were exported from Egypt and Gold and silver were mined in most European countries. These precious metals were exported to China to pay for Rome's imports of ceramics and silk. The Ricardian model is more relevant to the world economy before World War II. Modern trade theories are firm-based theories. Both of these categories, classical and modern, consist of several international trade theories. The Heckscher-Ohlin theory of comparative advantage was produced as an alternative to the Ricardian model of comparative advantage. It is also categorized under classical trade theories. The present paper focuses on the development and evaluation of the Heckscher-Ohlin theory of international trade.

The Heckscher-Ohlin theory (HO Model)

The Heckscher-Ohlin theory represents a method of explaining trade flows based on comparative advantage with multiple factors of production, commodities, and countries. The Heckscher-Ohlin model has been a very prominent theory of international trade since 1933. The earlier classical theory of absolute advantage and theory of comparative advantage assumed that open markets would lead countries and producers to determine which goods they could produce more efficiently with free trade. The absolute advantage and comparative advantage theory of trade explains the trade patterns using one factor of production. The

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standard H-O model begins by expanding the number of factors of production from one factor of production to two.

H.O model, developed by Swedish economists Eli Heckscher and Bertil Ohlin from the Stockholm School of Economics. The H-O model advances international trade theory by introducing the concept of factor endowments within a country as well as the underlying causes for differences. This model has been the central model of international trade theory, and it consists of two countries, two goods, and two factors of production. The Heckscher-Ohlin theory of international trade says that comparative advantage arises from the differences in countries' relative factor endowment. The country with higher relative proportions of a particular input factor will specialise in producing the good that intensively uses that factor, and import the other good (Clements, 2007). The H-O model explains comparative advantage in terms of the factor abundance of countries and the factor intensity of commodities (Salvatore, 2013). According to this model, the country exports the products which use their abundant and cheap factors of production and imports the products which use the countries' scarce factors (Mark, 1992). As stated by Ohlin, the countries should produce and export using two factors of production. The labour-endowed country can export labour-intensive commodities and the capital-endowed country exports capital-intensive commodities. Therefore, countries can produce and export capital-intensive goods or labour-intensive goods and gain mutual benefit from international trade. Thus indirectly, factors in abundant supply are exported and factors in scanty supply are imported. (Ohlin, 1933). This can happen with the differences in factor endowments of different countries and different factor proportions of producing different commodities. Therefore, The H-O theory is also known as the factor proportions theory or factor-endowment theory.

The Heckscher-Ohlin theory of international trade hypothesizes several assumptions. However, six are the most important in the theory. They are, (1) no transportation costs or trade barriers (2) perfect competition in both commodity and factor markets, (3) all production functions are homogeneous to the first degree (4) production functions are such that the two commodities always show different factor intensities, (5) production functions differ between commodities but are the same in both countries, and (6) tastes are the same in both countries. The model assumes that labour and capital are used in the production of two final goods. Capital factor refers to the physical machines and equipment that are used in production. The

important aspect of HO theory is the introduction of capital as the second factor of production. Two factors of production are considered more realistic in international trade theory.

There are number of significant differences between the classical and the modern approach in international trade theories. Ricardo and other classical economists argued that international trade between countries was based on differences in comparative costs. The absolute advantage and comparative advantage theories of trade consisted of the relative commodity prices of countries. Ricardo explained that differences in comparative costs arise from differences in skill and efficiency of labour. It is important to note that Heckscher and Ohlin agreed with this fundamental aspect of Ricardo's theory. Heckscher and Ohlin elaborated on this by explaining the factors which cause differences in the comparative costs of countries. The Heckscher-Ohlin theory makes a positive contribution to international economics. It makes a systematic attempt to explain the structure of international trade and reveals the base of international trade as the differences in factor endowments in different countries. The HO theory explains the real cause of the difference between trading countries. HO model pointed out differences in factor endowments of the nations and differences in factor proportions of producing different commodities, which account for differences in comparative costs. The Ricardian theory of comparative advantage failed to explain the causes of the differences in comparative costs. Blaug, (1992) stated that according to H. O's theory a country exports the goods whose production is intensive in the country's relatively abundant factor and imports other goods that use intensively in the country's relatively scarce factor. Differences in factor endowment in the countries are of basic significance in explaining international trade patterns. The H.O theory does not challenge or replace the comparative cost theory but it provides a sufficiently satisfactory explanation for differences in relative costs. The concept of factor endowment can be explained in two ways, either in terms of factor price or physical supply of factors.

Empirical Evaluations of the HO model

Various scholars have done many empirical evaluations of the HO model. Empirical testing began with Wassily Leontief (1953) performing the first empirical analysis for the Heckscher-Ohlin model. Leontief used USA trade data from 1947. According to the HO model, he assumed the USA was capital-abundant relative to the rest of the world. Since the USA was the most capital-abundant nation in the world, Leontief was the first to confront the H-O model that the capital-labour ratio embodied in the U.S. imports was higher than the capital-labour

ratio embodied in the U.S. exports. Leontief found out that the USA was an exporter of labour-intensive commodities and an importer of capital-intensive commodities. This is known as 'Leontief's Paradox.'

Vanek (1968) established the relationship between factor endowments and net exports. He proposed a test that could be performed on multi-country, multi-commodity and multifactor frameworks. In this method, the predictions were made based on the factor content of consumption and production, instead of considering the factor content of exports and imports. Brecher and Choudhri (1982), stated in their paper that international factor-price equalization is unnecessary for deriving the Heckscher-Ohlin theorem in its factor-content version. The factor-content version remains valid when the model is generalized to include trade impediments, intermediate goods or additional countries, except perhaps if the first of these extensions is combined with either of the other two. Woods (1994) argued that the H-O theorem is inaccurate in explaining global trade patterns. He argues that the traditional Heckscher-Ohlin theory probably provides a much better description of reality. He concludes that when the H-O theory is correctly specified excluding capital it provides an accurate and illuminating description of a large part of the global pattern of trade' (Woods, 1994:20). Trefler (1995) demonstrated the extent to which the predictions of the H-O-V model would confirm its validity if technological differences among the countries were taken into consideration.

Conclusion

The Heckscher-Ohlin theory of comparative advantage was produced as an alternative to the Ricardian model by removing the labour theory of value and incorporating the price mechanism into international trade theory. The model does not consider other important determinants of comparative advantages, such as technological innovation, entrepreneurship, and institutional factors. And also, the theory does not fully account for the role of technology, transportation costs, consumer preferences, government policies, or other factors that can influence trade patterns. However, this theory is still relevant today in understanding global trade. It is a simplified model of reality. The Heckscher-Ohlin theory provides a valuable framework for understanding the basic principles of international trade. The theory provides a framework for analyzing the factors that influence trade patterns and the potential benefits of international trade

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